

THE ROLE OF BRAIN IN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING

Aripova Shodiya Makhmudovna
German teacher of Fergana state university
Tuychiyev Jamoliddin Muhammadali ugli
Student of Fergana state university

***Annotation:** The article discusses the role of brain in language learning and its advantages.*

***Key words:** brain, language learning, learning process, improvement, language learner.*

INTRODUCTION

If you want to learn, you have to get enough sleep and nourishment. Long-term memories are mainly formed during sleep - it is also worth looking at the material before falling asleep.

For older students: Look to the left and right of the subject matter - greater context for understanding.

Talk about the subject matter, teach it to others - this changes processing, understanding and behavioral performance.

Cramming isn't always wrong—repetition improves the depth of learning.

Don't wait too long to do your homework - what's gone is gone, and the effort is less with fresh memories.

Stress is also an issue for children and young people – and just as harmful for them. Relaxation techniques work even at a young age and clear your head.

No multitasking when doing homework – the quickest way is this: deal with subject by subject and switch off all electronic devices and sources of interruption.

Movement is important – it supplies the brain with oxygen and reduces stress hormones.

MAIN PART

If parents, teachers, and students agree on anything, it's that fun classes support the learning process. Consistent. In recent years, this statement has been increasingly substantiated with results from brain research. So is there more laughter in the classroom today? That can be doubted. On the contrary: teachers are one of the hardest hit by burnout, while students also have to struggle with stress, but above all they are extremely distracted. And according to the unanimous opinion, they are always poorly trained.

The search for causes leads reflexively to the search for culprits. Anyone who talks to teachers learns that it's up to the students: they wouldn't be more enthusiastic about anything except Facebook, shooting games and painted fingernails - depending on gender. They can hardly be motivated and are only peripherally interested in training. It's a shame that many teachers feel this way about their students - especially when you consider who becomes a teacher: people with motivation and mission.

School psychologists have reported that the school psychological service has been abolished in Lower Saxony and other federal states. But even where it still exists, its staff has been thinned out and it answers very specific problems with standard emails. Getting an appointment in a private practice takes between three and six months. Not a good time for acute problems.

To round things off, the parents are on the list of potential culprits, as they are only busy with themselves and their work. So they let the teachers educate their children, but do not support their authority - on the contrary! – nor the learning process by taking it as an example.

All of this takes place in a school system that is not, let's say, very simple politically. Every federal state and every political party has its own ideas and goals, which are often only temporary, and which require a high degree of flexibility from

everyone involved: block lessons, comprehensive schools – the list of pedagogical fashions is long and not all of them make sense in the long term.

New old knowledge

In this cacophony of opinions, neuroscientific tones are increasingly echoing - findings from brain researchers who are now finding out how the learning machine in all of our heads actually works. They have found out a lot in recent years. It should be practical, it has to be relevant! And so neurodidactics has become an important word in pedagogy in recent years.

In fact, brain research has changed the way we look at learning. What was often experienced as an impertinence in the past – see the position of the students – is now an everyday neuronal process that begins with a furious overture in a baby, lasts a lifetime and does not necessarily end with age. Not only can the brain learn, it actually wants to! At a very basic level, learning is an inevitable consequence of perception. On a higher cognitive level, it is involved in a process that has a lot to do with joy. Well, that may not automatically apply to the conjugation of Latin verbs, but it works extremely well with the abilities of the heroes in the hottest computer game of the moment.

Motivation is the keyword, or even better: relevance! What is important to the brain, it absorbs. The preferences of the brain owner are therefore decisive, and these are in turn negotiated in the limbic system – another finding of brain research. There the seal of quality "important" is awarded, there learning becomes a happy experience. The fact that punishment should of course also be avoided is an important differentiation, and this also comes under motivation.

It is also important to brain research that every brain is different, so that every student learns differently - even if all of them do best while they sleep - and that the teacher has to get involved with each child individually. Which is not a small challenge in our school system and which very few teachers can implement.

The other tips are hardly more practical: Curiosity and motivation are not exactly new terms in education. The sleep thing is quite interesting, but much of the rest of neuroeducation is psychology, and known as such. The standard answer of some brain researchers is now: Yes, good teachers already know that, reform pedagogy anyway and the rest should finally stretch. Many a brain bestseller author lectures to himself and in his own frontal teaching past the target group. It is nevertheless understandable that the brain researchers speak out in a media-effective manner, because what they say is important to them. And last but not least, it is about the "raw material" of the future: our children.

But although many teachers are quite happy to have the neuroscientific background of their didactic efforts named in concrete terms, others are only minimally motivated by reproaches.

CONCLUSION

While the discussion is still going on here, let's take a quick look at another corner of the classroom that is also moving. And speak of time. A rare commodity for teachers and students in the face of a jam-packed curriculum, not just since G8.

REFERENCES

1. Xasanova O. Pedagogical Importance of Mnemotechnics in Increasing The Vocabulary Of Uzbek Language Learners in German Language //Science and Education. – 2021. – T. 1. – C. 1-6.
2. Rakhmonalievna A. G. The Role of Creativity in Foreign Language Lessons //International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 103-105.
3. Makhmudovna A. S. et al. THE CONTENT OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 39-40.

4. Makhmudovna A. S. Working with Texts in Grammar Lessons //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 261-263.
5. Makhmudovna A. S. CREATIVE WRITING IN GRAMMAR LESSONS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 258-260.
6. Siddikova N. B. Some opinions about problems encountered while playing in foreign language lessons //Science and Education. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 839-843.
7. Nuralieva S. USING BODY MOVEMENTS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. Special Issue 2. – C. 272-275.
8. Badirovna S. N., Habibullo J. HISTORICITY AND ART IN WORKS OF ABDULLAH QADIRI //world. – 2022. – T. 8. – №. 2.
9. Badirovna S. N. METHODS OF TEACHING GERMAN //Thematics Journal of English Language Teaching. – 2022. – T. 6. – №. 1.
10. Badirovna S. N. WORKING WITH SONGS IN GERMAN LESSONS //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 528-532.
11. Rakhmonalievna A. G. Vocabulary Learning Strategies in German as Foreign Language Lessons //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 339-341.
12. Xamidovna N. S. On The Influence of The Phonetic Laws of The Uzbek Language in The Teaching of German //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. – 2021. – T. 3. – C. 46-48.
13. Khamidovna N. S. On The Use of Infinitive Groups in German and Uzbek Languages //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 202-204.

14. Xasanova O. USING MNEMOTECHNICS IN TEACHING GERMAN ARTICLES FOR UZBEK STUDENTS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.
15. Хасанова О. К. К. ВИДЫ МНЕМОНИКИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ НЕМЕЦКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 40 (124).
16. Ibrokhimovich S. R., Mamatojievich M. A. TECHNIQUES FOR CREATIVE WRITING //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 493-496.
17. Vokhidovna K. K. Teaching Foreign Languages at Preschools //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 237-239.